

Analytical RP-HPLC Method Development and Its Validation for Estimation of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Formulation

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ABSTRACT

A very few analytical methods appeared in the literature for the determination of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate includes HPLC, HPTLC and UV- Visible spectrophotometric methods. In view of the above fact, some simple analytical methods were planned to develop with sensitivity, accuracy, precision and economical. In the present investigation HPLC method for the quantitative estimation of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate in bulk drug and per ICH guidelines pharmaceutical formulations has been developed. HPLC methods were validated as and results of linearity, precision, accuracy, Specificity, System suitability and robustness pass the limit. The HPLC method is more sensitive, accurate and precise compared to the previously reported method. There was no any interference of excipients in the recovery study. The low value of %RSD, molar extinction coefficient ($L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggested that the developed methods are sensitive.

Keywords: HPLC, linearity, precision, accuracy, Specificity.

INTRODUCTION

PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS

Pharmaceutical analysis is the branch of science which deals with identification of substances and determination of amount present in particular sample. Pharmaceutical analysis covers the bulk materials, dosage forms and more recently, biological samples in support of bio-pharmaceutical and pharmacokinetic studies. Analysis can be divided into areas called qualitative and quantitative analysis. Pharmaceutical products synthesized and identified using instrumental techniques.

The Laboratory controls shall include the establishment of sound and appropriate specification standards and test procedure to assure that the final drug substances conform to the required standards of identity, strength, quality and purity. Modern physical methods of analysis are extremely sensitive, providing precise and accurate information about the standards of chemicals or drugs up to monogram levels like HPLC.

The types of analysis can be distinguished in two ways:

Qualitative Analysis:

To refer identity of product, i.e., it yields useful clues from which the molecular or atomic species, the structural features, or the functional groups in the sample can be identified.

Quantitative Analysis:

To refer the purity of the product, i.e., the results are in the form of numerical data corresponding to the concentration of analyses.

INTRODUCTION TO CHROMATOGRAPHY

Chromatography is a technique to separate mixtures of substances into their components on the basis of their molecular structure and molecular composition. This involves a stationary phase (a solid, or a liquid supported on a solid) and a mobile phase (a liquid or a gas). The mobile phase flows through the stationary phase and carries the components of the mixture with

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it. Sample components that display stronger interactions with the stationary phase will move more slowly through the column than components with weaker interactions. This difference in rates causes the separation of various components. Chromatographic separations.

In 1970s in the US, Jim Waters founded Waters Corporation and started to sell HPLC instruments. This promoted the use of HPLC in practical analysis areas. The LC systems that Waters Corporation developed used high-pressure pump that generates rapid-flow of eluent, and thus resulted in dramatic improvement in the analysis time. Compared to the "low pressure chromatography" the newer types were called "high pressure liquid chromatography". Therefore, it was used to be thought that HPLC stands for High Pressure Liquid Chromatography, however nowadays it is a common agreement that HPLC stands for High Performance Liquid Chromatography. Another big change from Tswett's date was the data acquisition methods. Instead of observing the changes of layers by eyes, detector system was coupled to the LC and out-put was recorded on paper chart. If we were to demonstrate Tswett's analysis result on a chart (chromatogram), it will be like figure3. Initially, HPLC system was referred to Waters Corporation's system. Still now, Waters Corporation is the HPLC pioneer, but there are several other companies that manufacture and sell HPLC systems.

Technically speaking, the word LC represents all the Liquid Chromatography, including low pressure LC, however most LC systems used these days are HPLC thus often the word LC is used as comparable as HPLC.

Fig No. 1.1 Representation of Tswett's LC analysis

Types of HPLC:

There are following variants of HPLC, depending upon the phase system (stationary) in the process:

- **Normal Phase HPLC:**

This method separates analytes on the basis of polarity. NP-HPLC uses polar stationary phase and non-polar mobile phase. Therefore, the stationary phase is usually silica and typical mobile phases are hexane, methylene chloride, chloroform, diethyl ether, and mixtures of these. Polar samples are thus retained on the polar surface of the column packing longer than less polar materials.

- **Reverse Phase HPLC:**

The stationary phase is nonpolar (hydrophobic) in nature, while the mobile phase is a polar liquid, such as mixtures of water and methanol or acetonitrile. It works on the principle of hydrophobic interactions hence the more nonpolar the material is, the longer it will be retained.

- **Size-exclusion HPLC:**

The column is filled with material having precisely controlled pore sizes, and the particles are separated according to their molecular size. Larger molecules are rapidly washed through the column; smaller molecules penetrate inside the porous of the packing particles and elute later.

- **Ion-Exchange HPLC:**

The stationary phase has an ionically charged surface of opposite charge to the sample ions. This technique is used almost exclusively with ionic or ionizable samples. The stronger the charge on the sample, the stronger it will be attracted to the ionic surface and thus, the longer it will take to elute. The mobile phase is an aqueous buffer, where both pH and ionic strength are used to control elution time.

Fig No. 1.2 HPLC Components

4.1 Pump

In the earlier state of HPLC development, the pump was the most important part of the system. The development of HPLC can be said that it was a development of pump system. Pump is positioned in the most upper stream of the LC system and generates a flow of eluent from the solvent reservoir to the system. In the earlier stage of LC development, to be able to generate the high pressure was the one of the most important system requirements. However, nowadays, the high-pressure generation is a "standard" requirement and what is more concerned nowadays is to be able to provide a consistent pressure at any condition, to provide a controllable and reproducible flow rate. Since a change in the flow rate can influence the analysis largely.

4.2 Injector

An injector is placed next to the pump. The simplest method is to use a syringe, and the sample is introduced to the flow of eluent. Since the precision of LC measurement is largely affected by the reproducibility of sample injection, the design of injector is an important factor. The most widely used injection method is based on sampling loops. The use of autosampler (auto-injector) system is also widely used that allows repeated injections in a set scheduled-timing.

4.3 Column

The separation is performed inside the column; therefore, it can be said that the column is the heart of an LC system. The theory of chromatography column has not changed since Tswett's time; however there has been continuous improvement in column

development. The recent columns are often prepared in stainless steel housing, instead of glass columns used in Tswett's experiment. The packing material generally used is silica or polymer gels compared to calcium carbonate used by Tswett.

4.4 Detector

Separation of analytes is performed inside the column, whereas a detector is used to observe the obtained separation. The composition of the eluent is consistent when no analyte is present. While the presence of analyte changes the composition of the eluent. What detector does is to measure these differences. This difference is monitored as a form of electronic signal. There are different types of detectors available.

4.5 Recorder

The change in eluent detected by a detector is in the form of electronic signal, and thus it is still not visible to our eyes. In older days, pen (paper)-chart recorder was popularly used. Nowadays, computer-based data processor (integrator) is more common. There are various types of data processors; examples include a simple system consisting of in-built printer and word processor, and a personal computer type consisting of display monitor, keyboard, and printer. Also, there are software that are specifically designed for LC system. It provides not only data acquisition, but features like peak-fitting, base line correction, automatic concentration calculation, molecular weight determination, etc.

The components introduced so far are the basics of LC system. Below is some optional equipment used with the basic LC system.

4.6 Degasser

The eluent used for LC analysis may contain gases such as oxygen that are non-visible to our eyes. When gas is present in the eluent, this is detected as a noise the dissolved gas to move through the pores and remove the gas. Compared to and causes unstable baseline. Generally used method includes sparging (bubbling of inert gas), use of aspirator, distillation system, and/or heating and stirring. However, the method is not convenient and also when the solvent is left for a certain time period (e.g., during the long analysis), gas will dissolve back gradually. Degasser uses special polymer membrane tubing to remove gases. The numerous very small pores on the surface of the polymer tube allow the air to go through while preventing any liquid to go through the pore. By placing this tubing under low pressure container, it created pressure differences inside and outside the tubing (higher inside the tubing). This difference let classical batch type degassing, the degasser can be used on-line, it is more convenient and efficient. Many of new HPLC unit system contain a degasser.

4.7 Column Heater

The LC separation is often largely influenced by the column temperature. In order to obtain repeatable results, it is important to keep the consistent temperature conditions. Also, for some analysis, such as sugar and organic acid, better resolutions can be obtained at elevated temperature (50 to 80°C). It is also important to keep stable temperature to obtain repeatable results even it is analysed at around room temperature. There are possibilities that small different of temperature causes different separation results. Thus, columns are generally kept inside the column

- **Applications**

1. Detection of phenolic compounds in drinking water.
2. Bio-monitoring of pollutants.

can be obtained by HPLC includes resolution, identification and quantification of a compound. It also aids in chemical separation and purification. The other applications of HPLC include:

- **Pharmaceutical Applications**

1. To control drug stability.
- oven (column heater).

Application of HPLC:

The information that quality control.

- **Environmental**

2. Tablet dissolution study of pharmaceutical dosages form.
3. Pharmaceutical

Applications in Forensics

1. Quantification of drugs in biological samples.
2. Identification of steroids in blood, urine etc.
3. Forensic analysis of textile dyes.
4. Determination of cocaine and other drugs of abuse in blood, urine etc.

- **Food and Flavour**

1. Measurement of Quality of soft drinks and water.
2. Sugar analysis in fruit juices.
3. Analysis of polycyclic compounds in vegetables.
4. Preservative analysis.

- **Applications in Clinical Tests**

1. Urine analysis, antibiotics analysis in blood.
2. Analysis of bilirubin, biliverdin in hepatic disorders.
3. Detection of endogenous Neuropeptides in extracellular fluid of brain etc.

Method Validation

This process consists of establishments of the performance characteristics and the limitation of the method.

Method Performance Parameters are Determined using Equipment that is:

1. Within specification
2. Working correctly
3. Adequately calibrated

2. Revision of the established method
3. When established method are used in different laboratories and by different analysts etc.
4. Comparison of method
5. When quality control indicates method changes

Method Validation is required when:

1. A new method is being developed

DRUG PROFILE

Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate

Description	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (a prodrug of tenofovir), marketed by Gilead Sciences under the trade name Viroid, belongs to a class of antiretroviral drugs known as nucleotide analogue reverse transcriptase inhibitors (nRTIs). This drug is prescribed in combination with other drugs in the management of HIV infection as well as in Hepatitis B therapy. Tenofovir disoproxil was initially approved in 2001. Generic Name: Tenofovir disoproxil Brand Names: Viread, Vemlidy, and others when combined with other antiretrovirals
Structure	<p>Figure 2.1: Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate Structure</p>
IUPAC Name:	bis ({{[(propan-2-yloxy)carbonyl]oxy}methyl) {{[(2R)-1-(6-amino-9H-purin-9-yl)propan-2-yl]oxy}methanephosphonate.
Chemical Formula:	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ N ₅ O ₁₀ P
Molecular weight:	Average: 519.44 Monoisotopic: 519.17
pKa	Strongest Acidic: 8.49 Strongest Basic: 7.22
Appearance	White colour powder
Solubility	It is insoluble in water but is freely soluble in methanol and soluble in 95% ethanol.
Category	Anti-HIV Agents Anti-Infective Agents Anti-Retroviral Agents Anti-infective for Systemic Use Antiviral Agents.
Mechanism of Action	Tenofovir disoproxil is converted to tenofovir diphosphate in the body, which inhibits HIV-1 reverse transcriptase and hepatitis B virus polymerase by competing with the natural substrate deoxyadenosine 5'-triphosphate. This results in the termination of the DNA chain and prevents viral replication.
Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics	Pharmacokinetics: Unknown Pharmacodynamics: Tenofovir disoproxil is a blood schizonticide active against erythrocytic stages of Plasmodium falciparum. It is thought that administration of Tenofovir disoproxil with artemether results in cooperate antimalarial clearing

	effects. Artemether has a rapid onset of action and is rapidly cleared from the body. It is thus thought to provide rapid symptomatic relief by reducing the number of malarial parasites. Tenofovir disoproxil has a much longer half-life and is believed to clear residual parasites.
Metabolism	Tenofovir disoproxilfumarate is heavily metabolized in the liver by the CYP3A4 enzyme. ^{12,13} Two metabolites have been identified.
Route of eliminatio	Tenofovir disoproxilfumarate is believed to be excreted in the bile and feces. In healthy volunteers who have achieved steady-state concentrations of Tenofovir disoproxilfumarate, the unchanged drug was excreted at 9% of the ingested dose, and excretion of its carboxylic metabolite under was measured at 4% of the ingested dose. Concentrations of other metabolites could not be determined.
Half-life	The overall mean terminal half-life of Tenofovir disoproxil is 4.5 days.
Indications	Treatment of HIV-1 infection in combination with other antiretroviral agents. Treatment of chronic hepatitis B in adults and pediatric patients 12 years and older..
Absorption	Food increases absorption.
Dosage and Administration	HIV-1 Infection: 300 mg once daily, in combination with other antiretroviral agents. Chronic Hepatitis B: 300 mg once daily. Dosage adjustments may be required in patients with renal impairment.
Protein binding	The binding of Tenofovir disoproxilfumarate to plasma proteins is over 98%
Adverse Effects	Common: Nausea, diarrhea, headache, dizziness, fatigue, depression, rash. Serious: Lactic acidosis, severe hepatomegaly with steatosis, renal toxicity, including acute renal failure and Fanconi syndrome, bone mineral density loss.
Drug Interactions	Avoid concurrent use with other nephrotoxic agents to reduce the risk of renal toxicity. Use with other antiviral drugs should be based on an understanding of drug interactions and pharmacodynamics.
Monitoring and Safety	Regular monitoring of renal function (serum creatinine and phosphorus). Monitoring bone mineral density in patients with a history of bone fractures or other risk factors. Liver function tests to monitor for hepatotoxicity. Monitoring for signs of lactic acidosis and hepatomegaly
Clinical Trials and Research	Numerous clinical trials have demonstrated the efficacy of tenofovir disoproxil in the treatment of HIV-1 and chronic hepatitis B, both as monotherapy and in combination with other antiretroviral agents. Ongoing research continues to explore its long-term safety and efficacy, as well as its use in pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) for HIV.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

6.1. Material:

Table 6.1: Active Pharmaceutical Drug

Sr. No.	Name	Description
1.	Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate	White powder, use to treat chronic hepatitis B and to prevent and treat HIV/AIDS
2.	Ricovir Tablet	300 mg drug contain each tablet, Manufactured by Mylan Laboratories Limited, Marketed by Mylan Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd.

Table 6.2: List of Chemicals use in Research work

Sr No.	Name of Chemical	Molecular Formula	Properties	Manufacturer
1.	Acetonitrile	C ₂ H ₃ N	Solvent, BP 76-81.6°C	Merck Life science
2.	Methanol	CH ₃ OH	Flammable Solvent	Merck Life science
3.	Phosphate Buffer	KH ₂ PO ₄	Buffer	Rankem
4.	Distilled Water	H ₂ O	Universal Solvent, BP 100°C	Inhouse

ListTable 6.3: List of instruments

Sr. No.	Name of Equipment's/ Instruments	Model /Specification	Manufacturer
1	HPLC	Shimadzu LC2030	Shimadzu (I prominence plus)
	Pump	Binary Gradient	
	Sample Injection Port	Autosampler	
	UV/Vis Detector	UV 2030 plus	
	Software	LabSolutuion	
2	pH Meter	101	Chemiline
3	Balance	AY-120	Shimadzu
4	Sonicator	UCB-40	Rolex
5	Deep Freezer	-	Blue Star
6	Refrigerator	-	Godrej

6.2 Methods

Preliminary Analysis of Drug

a) Description

Color and texture of Tenofovir was compared with reported characters mentioned in drug bank.

b) Solubility

Solubility of Tenofovir was determined in various solvents like water, methanol, ethanol and Acetonitrile.

c) UV Analysis

UV analysis was carried out by scanning the solution of Tenofovir at 200-400 nm.

6.3. Method Development:

Chromatographic Conditions

During mobile phase optimization Methanol: Water in the ratio of 50:50 was found to be satisfactory for Tenofovir. The low-pressure gradient mode at a flow rate of 1.0ml/min at ambient temperature was

used. The mobile phase was degassed and filtered through membrane filter (0.22µ). The injection volume was 10 µL and the run time for the analysis was 8 minutes. The detection was carried out at 260 nm using PDA detector.

Preparation of standard stock solution

Accurately weighed quantity of Tenofovir (100 mg) were transferred into two separate 100ml volumetric flask containing 60ml Diluent. The content was dissolved by sonication for 5 mins. The volume was made up to the mark with Diluent. It was further diluted appropriately using diluent to get desired concentrations.

Preparation of Sample solution and Assay of marketed formulation

Accurately weighed about 53 mg of tablet powder was transferred to 100 ml of volumetric flask containing 60ml of Diluent. The sample was dissolved by sonication for 15 mins and volume was made up to the mark with Diluent. The resulting solution was filtered using membrane filter 0.22µ. This diluted sample was then analyzed by HPLC.

Trial-1

System	Shimadzu HPLC series 2030 I prominence
Stationary Phase	Thermo Scientific C ₁₈ (150×4.6×5μ)
Mobile phase	Acetonitrile: Water (50:50)
pH	-
Detection wavelength	260nm
Run time	15.00 Minutes
Retention time	11.375 Minutes
Flow rate	1.0 mL / min.
Injection volume	10 μL
Column Temperature	Ambient

Figure 6.1: Chromatogram of Trail 1

Observation: All properties of peak are very poor, Splitting of peak observed and tailing is observed therefore peak not selected.

Trial-2

System	Shimadzu HPLC series 2030 I prominence
Stationary Phase	Thermo Scientific C ₁₈ (150×4.6×5μ)
Mobile phase	Acetonitrile : Buffer (50:50)
pH	-
Detection wavelength	260nm
Run time	8.00 Minutes
Retention time	4.603 Minutes
Flow rate	1.0 mL / min.
Injection volume	10 μL
Column Temperature	Ambient

Figure 6.2: Chromatogram of Trail 2

Observation: Peak is broad and more tailing as well, peak shape is not proper moreover poor peak properties. Peak not selected.

Trial-3

System	Shimadzu HPLC series 2030 I prominence
Stationary Phase	Thermo Scientific C ₁₈ (150×4.6×5μ)
Mobile phase	Methanol: Buffer (50:50)
pH	-
Detection wavelength	260nm
Run time	18.00 Minutes
Retention time	13.634 Minutes
Flow rate	1.0 mL / min.
Injection volume	10 μL
Column Temperature	Ambient

Figure 6.3: Chromatogram of Trail 3

Observation: More retention time, tailing is observed also the base line is not proper, hence Peak was rejected.

Trial-4

System	Shimadzu HPLC series 2030 I prominence
Stationary Phase	Thermo Scientific C ₁₈ (150×4.6×5μ)
Mobile phase	Acetonitrile: Methanol: Buffer (50:50)
pH	4.0
Detection wavelength	260nm
Run time	15.00 Minutes
Retention time	11.358 Minutes
Flow rate	1.0 mL / min.
Injection volume	10 μL
Column Temperature	Ambient

Figure 6.4: Chromatogram of Trail 4

Observation: Peak is satisfactory, But more retention time, Peak properties are good, Peak not selected.

Trial-5

System	Shimadzu HPLC series 2030 I prominence
Stationary Phase	Thermo Scientific C ₁₈ (150×4.6×5μ)
Mobile phase	Methanol: Water (50:50)
pH	-
Detection wavelength	260nm
Run time	15.00 Minutes
Retention time	9.473 Minutes
Flow rate	1.0 mL / min.
Injection volume	10 μL
Column Temperature	Ambient

Figure 6.5: Chromatogram of Trail 5

Observation:

Extremely satisfactory peak, all peak properties are good, less retention time than other trials. Moreover less tailing factor and more theoretical plates.

Peak Selected Optimized Chromatographic Condition.

METHOD VALIDATION

The proposed HPLC method was validated in terms of system suitability, specificity, precision, accuracy

and robustness as per the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines (7).

1. Linearity:

The linearity of peak area response for Tenofovir was determined from 20 % to 120 % level of working concentration of Tenofovir. The stock solutions of standard Tenofovir was diluted to six different known concentrations. Linearity graph of concentration (as x-value) versus area (as y-value) were plotted and correlation coefficient, y-intercept and slope of the regression were calculated.

Table 7.1: Linearity Result of Tenofovir

Sr.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Peak Area
		Tenofovir
1	20	684988
2	40	1369564
3	60	2004234
4	80	2739563
5	100	3424422
6	120	4109453

Figure 7.2: A Typical Chromatogram of Linearity level 1

Figure 7.1: Calibration Curve of Tenofovir

Figure 7.3: A Typical Chromatogram of Linearity level 2

Figure 7.6: A Typical Chromatogram of Linearity level 5

Figure 7.4: A Typical Chromatogram of Linearity level 3

Figure 7.7: A Typical Chromatogram of Linearity level 6

Figure 7.5: A Typical Chromatogram of Linearity level 4

Table 7.2: Characteristic parameters of Tenofovir for the proposed HPLC method.

Parameter	Result
	Tenofovir
Calibration range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	20-120
Detection wavelength (nm)	260
Solvent (Methanol: Water)	60:40
Regression equation (y^*)	$y = 34319x - 13333$
Slope (b)	34319
Intercept (a)	13333
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9998
Limit of Detection ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.1756
Limit of Quantitation ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	6.5926

System Suitability:

System-suitability tests are an integral part of method development and are used to ensure adequate performance of the chromatographic system.

Retention time (R_t), number of theoretical plates (N) and tailing factor (T) were evaluated for six replicate injections of the drug at a concentration of $50 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The results which are given in Table 7.3 were within acceptable limits.

Table 7.3: System suitability studies of Tenofovir by HPLC method.

Sr. No.	Properties	Values
1.	Retention time	9.40
2.	Area	11244
3.	Asymmetry	1.3

Specificity:**Table 7.4: Specificity of Tenofovir by HPLC method**

Specificity				
Sample	Label Claim (mg)	Amount Found	Recovery	Retention Time
Tablet	300	299.91	99.97	9.42

Table 7.5: Tenofovir Marketed Formulation

Formulation	
Name of Formulation	Ricovir
Type of Formulation	Tablet
Concentration (mg)	300

Figure 7.9: A typical chromatogram of Tenofovir Standard [Concentration 20ug/ml]

Chromatogram of blank was taken as shown in Figure 7.4 Chromatogram of Tenofovir showed peak at a retention time of 6.223 min. The mobile phase designed for the method resolved the drug very efficiently. The Retention time of Tenofovir was 6.223 ± 0.0098 min. The wavelength 260 nm was selected for detection because; it resulted in better detection sensitivity for the drug. The peak for Tenofovir from the tablet formulation was Tenofovir.

Figure 7.10: A typical chromatogram of Tenofovir Sample [Concentration 20ug/ml]**Sensitivity:**

The sensitivity of measurement of Tenofovir by use of the proposed method was estimated in terms of the limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ). The LOD and LOQ were calculated by the use of signal to noise ratio. In order to estimate the LOD and LOQ values, the blank sample was injected six times and the peak area of this blank was calculated as noise level. The LOD was calculated as three times the noise level, while ten times the noise value gave the LOQ. LOD and LOQ were found to be 2.1756 and 6.5926 respectively.

Precision:

Demonstration of precision was done under two categories. The injection repeatability (System Precision) was assessed by using six injections of the

standard solution of Tenofovir and the % RSD of the replicate injections was calculated. In addition, to demonstrate the precision of method (Method Precision), six samples from the same batch of formulation were analysed individually and the assay content of each sample was estimated. The average

for the six determinations was calculated along with the % RSD for the replicate determinations. Both the system precision and method precision were subjected for intra-day variations as reported in Table 7.6 respectively.

Table 7.6: Intraday Precision of Tenofovir at 260

Precision			
Sr. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Intraday	Interday
1	80	2745232	2795322
2	80	2738443	2805523
3	80	2742232	2866758
4	80	2724133	2882192
5	80	2795022	2892023
6	80	2742424	2901912
Average		2748032.2	2857304
Standard Deviation		22140.80	41712.85
RSD%		0.8057	1.460

Accuracy:

Recovery studies by the standard addition method were performed with a view to justify the accuracy of the proposed method. Previously analysed samples of Tenofovir (20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were spiked with 80, 100, and

120 % extra Tenofovir standard and the mixtures were analysed by the proposed method.

Standard deviation of the % recovery and % RSD were calculated and reported in Table 7.7

Table 7.7: Accuracy of Tenofovir at 260 nm.

Recovery				
Sr. No	Amount of Sample	Amount of Drug Added	Amount of Drug Recovered	Recovery %
	($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	
1	80	40	39.982	99.95
2	80	80	79.99	99.98
3	80	120	120.01	100.08

Robustness:

Robustness is a measure of capacity of a method to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variations in the method conditions, and is indications of the reliability of the method. A method is robust, if it is unaffected by small changes in operating conditions. To determine the robustness of this method, the experimental conditions were deliberately altered at

three different levels and retention time and chromatographic response were evaluated. One factor at a time was changed to study the effect. Variation of mobile phase composition (Acetonitrile: Water and Acetonitrile: buffer) and mobile phase flow rate by 0.9 ml/min (0.8 and 1 ml/min) had no significant effect on the retention time and chromatographic response of the 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution, indicating that the method was robust. The results are shown in Table 7.8

Table 7.8: Robustness of Tenofovir at 260 nm

Sr. No	Parameter	Response	Parameter	Response
	Methanol: Water	Retention Time (min)	Detection Wavelength	Peak Area

(V/V)		(nm)			
1	59	41	9.554	258	2681567
2	60	40	9.467	260	2739674
3	61	39	9.356	262	2773456
Average			9.427	Average	2731645
Standard Deviation			0.080	Standard Deviation	37850.36
RSD%			0.849	RSD%	1.386

CONCLUSION

For routine analytical purpose, it is always necessary to establish methods capable of analysing huge number of samples in a short time period with due accuracy and precision. Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate is official in Indian Pharmacopoeia.

A very few analytical methods appeared in the literature for the determination of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate includes HPLC, HPTLC and UV-Visible spectrophotometric methods. In view of the above fact, some simple analytical methods were planned to develop with sensitivity, accuracy, precision and economical. In the present investigation HPLC method for the quantitative estimation of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate in bulk drug and per ICH guidelines pharmaceutical formulations has been developed. HPLC methods were validated as and results of linearity, precision, accuracy, Specificity, System suitability and robustness pass the limit. The HPLC method is more sensitive, accurate and precise compared to the previously reported method. There was no any interference of excipients in the recovery study. The low value of %RSD, molar extinction coefficient ($L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggested that the developed methods are sensitive. The proposed high-performance liquid chromatographic method has also been evaluated over the accuracy, precision and robustness and proved to be convenient and effective for the quality control of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate. Developed method was found simple and cost effective for the quality control of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate.

Moreover, the lower solvent consumption leads to a cost effective and environmentally friendly Spectroscopic procedure. Thus, the proposed methodology is rapid, selective, requires a simple sample preparation procedure, and represents a good procedure for Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate.

SUMMARY

The contents of the thesis have been divided into 9 chapters and appropriate references have been placed after the 10th chapter.

RPHPLC method was developed for the estimation of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate in Pharmaceutical Formulation.

- Designed of Experiment by Literature survey and done trial and found result found were within limit.
- Optimized and Developed method for Spectrophotometry.
- RPHPLC method was validated for Linearity, Accuracy, Interday & Intraday Precision, Specificity & Selectivity, Sensitivity, and Robustness.
- Designed of Experiment.
- Optimized and Developed method for Chromatography.

The developed method were successfully applied to determine the drugs in Pharmaceutical Formulation.

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